

DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR OBJECT DETECTION

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Abstract. Data provides each node with information in the form of inputs. The node multiplies the inputs with random weights, calculates them, and adds a bias. Finally, nonlinear functions, also known as activation functions, are applied to determine which neuron to fire.

Key words: inputs, a bias, algorithm, layer, Network, Radial, LSTM, RNNs, output.

While deep learning algorithms feature self-learning representations, they depend upon ANNs that mirror the way the brain computes information. During the training process, algorithms use unknown elements in the input distribution to extract features, group objects, and discover useful data patterns. Much like training machines for self-learning, this occurs at multiple levels, using the algorithms to build the models.

Deep learning models make use of several algorithms. While no one network is considered perfect, some algorithms are better suited to perform specific tasks. To choose the right ones, it is good to gain a solid understanding of all primary algorithms.

A Cyber security Boot Camp serves as a gateway for individuals to delve into the intricate world of deep learning algorithms within the context of cybersecurity.

Defining neural networks

1. The input layer(s)

2. The hidden layer(s)
3. The output layer(s)

Figure 1. Steps of neural network's work.

Participants in this program gain insights into how deep learning techniques can be employed to enhance threat detection, anomaly recognition, and predictive analysis.

1. Types of Algorithms used in Deep Learning
2. List of top 10 deep learning algorithms:
3. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)
4. Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs)
5. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)
6. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)
7. Radial Basis Function Networks (RBFNs)
8. Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs)
9. Self Organizing Maps (SOMs)
10. Deep Belief Networks (DBNs)
11. Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBMs)
12. Autoencoders

Deep learning algorithms work with almost any kind of data and require large amounts of computing power and information to solve complicated issues.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)

RNNs have connections that form directed cycles, which allow the outputs from the LSTM to be fed as inputs to the current phase.

The output from the LSTM becomes an input to the current phase and can memorize previous inputs due to its internal memory. RNNs are commonly used for image captioning, time-series analysis, natural-language processing, handwriting recognition, and machine translation.

Figure 2. An unfolded RNN.

Work strategies of RNNs:

1. The output at time $t-1$ feeds into the input at time t ;
2. Similarly, the output at time t feeds into the input at time $t+1$;
3. RNNs can process inputs of any length;
4. The computation accounts for historical information, and the model size does not increase with the input size;

5. Here is an example of how Google’s auto-completing feature works:

Figure 3. Works of Google’s auto-completing feature.

REFERENCES

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